

Machine learning classification of geomorphometric segments for floodplain detection and delineation

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Abstract—We propose a floodplain detection and delineation workflow based on the Copernicus DEM. It involves watershed segmentation of slope and a machine learning algorithm - Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) model, for the geomorphometric variables of the segments. For the method's accuracy, spatially separated training and testing areas were used to assess the generalization power. Seven classes of landforms were labeled to allow the MLP model to statistically identify the flat floodplain class in the feature space compared to the adjacent channels, hillslopes, and levees. The confusion matrix data shows good generalization power with 94% accuracy for the floodplain class detection. The results show promising perspectives to solve the problem of quaternary deposits mapping and flood risk assessment.

to a 20 m resolution in EPSG: 3844 projection for the Eastern part of Romania (Fig. 1). The 20 m resolution is a natural choice since the pixel size in EPSG: 4326 projection is roughly a rectangle of 60 by 20 meters at the latitude and longitude of Romania. The choice of the study area is related to the low forest coverage.

Since the elevation data comes from radar measurements, the landform shape in non-vegetated areas is well-constrained. The Copernicus DEM has low noise in flat areas and excellent precision, similar to LiDAR data (Fig. 2). At the 20 m spatial resolution, the channel and floodplain of rivers up to the third Strahler order are recognizable.

I. INTRODUCTION

Floodplains and their morphology, including river channels and fluvial terraces, are important landforms with practical implications from many perspectives: quaternary geology/geomorphological mapping, flood risks, and planning.

The availability of a medium-resolution Digital Elevation Model (DEM) like Copernicus DEM opens up the possibility of delineating channels and floodplains with better accuracy than with SRTM or other similar DEMs.

We used a machine learning approach to classify the floodplain slope segments. Specifically, we used Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), a feedforward artificial neural network (ANN) algorithm that relies on changing the weights of the morphometric variables after each process to determine the landform type based on the amount of error in the output compared to the expected result.

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A. Materials

The DEM used for testing the proposed approach is a crop of the worldwide Copernicus DEM (GLO30), which was resampled

B. Methods

The segments used to delineate the landforms in the study area were generated by the watershed segmentation in SAGA GIS [1]. ViGRA implementation [2] in SAGA GIS was used on

Figure 1. Location of study area within Romania.

the slope morphometrical variable. This approach generates segments that adequately describe the landforms by producing sharp boundaries between hillslopes and channels/floodplains (Fig. 3). Segments cover well even the burial mounds and levees.

For reference to estimate the accuracy of the approach, we have classified the segments into seven classes: channels, floodplains, gentle and steep hillslopes, plateaus, terraces, and ridges (Fig. 4). We excluded the areas where there is forest cover or edited reservoir mask (non-colored areas in Fig. 4).

Figure 2. Topographic cross-section through the Jijia floodplain (bottom) and the LiDAR (top left) and COPDEM (top right) data associated with it.

Figure 3. Examples of watershed slope segmentation results overlaid on the shaded dem (a,c) or slope (b,d) for a floodplain sector (a,b) and a hillslope sector (c, d).

Figure 4. Landform classification.

For the segments, descriptive statistics (minimum, maximum, mean, range, variance, standard deviation) of various geomorphometric variables (elevation, index of convergence, openness, slope, full set of curvatures, flow length measures, TWI, texture, roughness, altitude relative to local channels) were generated to train a neural network, specifically Multilayer Perceptron (MLP). MLP is a deep feedforward neural network/multilayer perceptron method that uses the neuron model, of acyclic networks, in layers that use connected functions as vector nodes to fit linear functions for an overall non-linear classification or regression. R stat [3] and kerasR package [4,5] were used for the MLP implementation.

In Figure 5, we show by color the landforms class in the statistic space defined by the mean values of segment slope and flow path length. It can be observed that floodplains and gentle and steep slopes have an excellent definition in the feature space, while the other landforms classes spread all over. This situation reflects the geomorphometric characteristics of the segmentation: channel segments also spread on the bottom of the hillslopes, while the plateaus and ridges spread on the hillslope's upper part.

In order to test the generalization power of the MLP model, we split the study area into two rectangular parts, the northern one for training and the southern one for testing.

Figure 5. Landform distribution.

III. RESULTS

The results of the MLP fitting show that with at least 50 epochs, the accuracy is relatively stable (Fig. 6). Similar results are obtained while tuning various parameters of the MLP.

The confusion matrices and their statistics (Tables I-IV) show a good power of generalization, especially for floodplains, gentle and steep hillslopes, and plateaus and ridges. Channels and terraces are the landform types that show the lowest.

The true positive of floodplain class segments (Fig. 7) covers the floodplains in the study area very well. Looking at the false positives and false negatives of the floodplain class (Fig. 7), which is the one that interests us, it can be observed that these segments either are scattered and can be easily filtered, or they are well-delineated from the floodplain and again can be easily identified and eventually filtered.

Figure 4. Line plots of learning curves for the MLP model: cross-entropy loss (top), classification accuracy (bottom).

TABLE I. CONFUSION MATRIX OF THE TRAINING AREA.

		Reference Landforms						
		<i>C</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>G</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>R</i>
Predicted Landforms	<i>C</i>	2585	65	199	140	1 ^a	4	13
	<i>F</i>	1238	10383	399	4	0	24	0
	<i>G</i>	83	10	3789	694	621	110	50
	<i>S</i>	82	0	37	11014	1	0	27
	<i>P</i>	3	0	561	12	3972	7	52
	<i>T</i>	25	0	100	2	19	1210	0
	<i>R</i>	1	0	311	142	676	9	957

a. *C* – channels, *F* – floodplains, *G* – gentle hillslopes, *S* – steep hillslopes, *P* – plateaus, *T* – terraces, *R* – ridges

TABLE II. CONFUSION MATRIX FOR THE TESTING AREA.

		Landforms						
		<i>C</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>G</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>R</i>
Prediction	<i>C</i>	2656	96	212	48	17	27	31
	<i>F</i>	1643	9286	870	11	16	346	0
	<i>G</i>	138	9	4545	648	670	321	75
	<i>S</i>	134	0	58	8431	2	0	31
	<i>P</i>	27	0	537	5	5395	430	69
	<i>T</i>	3	1	198	0	204	812	1
	<i>R</i>	37	0	159	39	471	99	773

a. *C* – channels, *F* – floodplains, *G* – gentle hillslopes, *S* – steep hillslopes, *P* – plateaus, *T* – terraces, *R* – ridges

TABLE III. STATISTICS OF CONFUSION MATRIX IN THE TRAINING AREA.

		Landforms						
		<i>C</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>G</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>R</i>
Sensitivity		0.64	0.99	0.70	0.92	0.75	0.89	0.87
Specificity		0.99	0.94	0.95	0.99	0.98	0.97	0.97
Pos Pred Value		0.86	0.86	0.71	0.99	0.86	0.89	0.46
Neg Pred Value		0.96	0.99	0.95	0.97	0.96	0.99	0.99
Prevalence		0.10	0.26	0.14	0.30	0.13	0.03	0.03
Detection Rate		0.07	0.26	0.1	0.28	0.1	0.03	0.02
Detection Prevalence		0.08	0.30	0.14	0.28	0.11	0.03	0.05
Balanced Accuracy		0.82	0.97	0.83	0.96	0.87	0.94	0.92

a. *C* – channels, *F* – floodplains, *G* – gentle hillslopes, *S* – steep hillslopes, *P* – plateaus, *T* – terraces, *R* – ridges

TABLE IV. STATISTICS OF CONFUSION MATRIX IN THE TESTING AREA.

		Landforms						
		<i>C</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>G</i>	<i>S</i>	<i>P</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>R</i>
Sensitivity		0.57	0.99	0.70	0.92	0.80	0.40	0.79
Specificity		0.99	0.90	0.94	0.99	0.97	0.99	0.98
Pos Pred Value		0.86	0.76	0.71	0.97	0.83	0.67	0.49
Neg Pred Value		0.95	0.99	0.94	0.98	0.96	0.97	0.99
Prevalence		0.12	0.24	0.17	0.23	0.17	0.05	0.02
Detection Rate		0.07	0.023	0.11	0.21	0.14	0.02	0.02
Detection Prevalence		0.08	0.31	0.16	0.22	0.16	0.03	0.04
Balanced Accuracy		0.78	0.95	0.82	0.96	0.88	0.70	0.88

a. *C* – channels, *F* – floodplains, *G* – gentle hillslopes, *S* – steep hillslopes, *P* – plateaus, *T* – terraces, *R* – ridges

IV. DISCUSSIONS

The main objective of this research approach is detecting and delineating floodplain areas from medium-resolution DEMs on large areas. The proposed method is to use segments in order to have crisp borders for the delineation. The watershed segmentation of the slope delineates very well the border between the flat floodplain and the adjacent hillslopes and the levees inside the floodplain. A wide range of geomorphometrical variables are used as input for training an MLP model, and the results are good enough for this research stage. More variables could be tested in a tuning approach, and some class accuracy might be improved. Although terraces are well delineated from the floodplains, some terrace levels are still mapped as floodplains. These issues will be solved in the next steps of the analysis, during which the results will be used to derive the extension of the floodplain through merging and filtering.

Figure 5. Predicted floodplain class according to the confusion matrix categories (False positives and false negatives).

V. CONCLUSIONS

The proposed approach of machine learning classification of landform segments proved helpful in detecting and delineating some landform types. Not all the landform types have the same accuracy, but using them allows the model to discriminate them geomorphometrically and better describe the other classes. This case is specific to floodplains and channels, which are very well-identified and can be easily delineated by simply merging and filtering polygon islands or visual inspection. Also, the delineation accuracy between floodplain and hillslope segments is well-defined.

Considering the Quaternary age of the floodplains and terraces, with most of the floodplains dating as Holocene, their geomorphometric delineation can be used as the base of their mapping. Geologic maps can be updated to incorporate this information to characterize Quaternary deposits better. As dating information improves and significantly better geological or

geophysical data piles up, surface landform delineation will also be essential for the depth and volume prediction of these deposits.

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